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Abstract

In the current economic scenario, money plays an important role as spare funds are essential to deal with future crises. The main focus of this study is to assess the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in accelerating the transformation of the global services industry, known as financial technology (FinTech). The areas covered in this study are AI highly capable and accessible FinTech services, challenges faced during transformation, and policy and regulatory recommendations for AI and FinTech services. The purpose of saving money is to invest it in FinTech products and services to get more profit in the long run. However, there is even greater confusion among individuals when it comes to acquiring knowledge. This also takes time, as investors cannot process the information available. This is one of the issues that needs to be investigated using data mining techniques in stock market prediction. The main objective of this research study is to predict and model the future price of a stock index (SMI) using AI techniques based on past price information. Additionally, it is important to have a comprehensive overview of existing investment opportunities to make appropriate financial investment decisions. The results show that various hybrids and AI applied to the stock market are the most common combinations, and many types of research are new attempts to predict future market movements and values. This method achieves a return of approximately 20% per year, considering all holdings, and is less risky than the base.

Keywords: Investors Attitude, Financial Investment, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Stock Market Index.

1. Introduction

Financial markets are the most important pillars of a country's economy. The Indian financial market is the largest contributor to the growth of the Indian economy. Capital markets play a very important role in the economy because they apply a unified mechanism to help businesses, governments, and financial companies raise funds. It does a great job of converting personal and commercial savings into investments and generates a variety of financial real estate ideas. One of the segments of the capital markets is the stock market, which serves as a platform for purchasing and marketing stocks, mutual funds, and other financial instruments. A suitable environment for national growth depends on a healthy stock market. The stock market plays an important role in properly investing hard-earned savings and connecting savers with stakeholders. Allocating a portion of your savings to businesses improves stock market

performance, which is reflected in faster stock price growth. Predicting stock price performance is one of the most interesting topics when analysing time series data. How to accurately predict stock price performance is an open question related to financial institutions and the education sector.

Prediction of stock performance is considered to be a complex process as it is sophisticated, dynamic and involves many ambiguous and interrelated factors. The original pioneers are economic analysts and stock traders who predict the performance of stock prices.

Additionally, fewer expenses and more investment in liquid, high-yield securities are reasons why multiple high-yield securities are available. With the help of stock markets, the world economy is becoming integrated through the penetration of foreign portfolio investment (FPI) and foreign institutional investor (FII) based investments. Financial markets around the world are experiencing rapid, decisive and exclusive changes. In addition, systems are also subject to technological change, and the vast amount of information available within the operational boundaries of global markets is stimulating incredible change.

Artificial neural networks (ANN), genetic algorithms (GA), support vector regression (SVR), and hybrid models are some of the machine learning (ML) models that have been widely used in financial time series forecasting in recent years. This study shows that approaches differ depending on the number and type of variables used to model economic behavior. However, it remains to be determined which input variables can best be used. Moreover, guidelines for creating dynamic and intelligent trading systems have not yet been established. The emerging FinTech market is seeing significant growth in AI capabilities and ML. The latest technologies, services, companies, etc. are broadly referred to as "Fintech." This consists of (but is not bound to) blockchain¹, cryptocurrencies, smart contracts, robo-advice, AI platforms, crowdfunding, and mobile payments. In financial services and FinTech, AI topped the mainstream list in 2017.

Although different financial markets and services perform many different activities, they have two key elements in common. (i) The interactions between different actors with different motivations, and (ii) the information these actors use to make decisions. The second key element, information, is the most important driver of financial transactions and risk management. In fact, we are "never alone" in the marketplace, as every type of transaction always involves different parties, such as buyers and sellers. Because buyers and sellers have different needs and information, they are willing to make opposing and seemingly contradictory buying and selling decisions. Information is also a key element of risk management, the practice of mitigating the effects of stochastic fluctuations in the prices and values of assets.

In this research, we will use AI technology to predict future stock prices, formulate the following hypotheses, and attempt to evaluate the research results. The study also conducted a study of the important variables of stock market indices and a study to predict the performance of stock prices to enhance returns and reduce investment challenges. Empirical analysis of machine learning used in stock selection has shown promising results. However, compared to various other research findings, the merits of our study are uncertain, which may be due to our emphasis on investability and interpretability. Investors should approach machine learning with reasonable expectations. As competitive markets evolve and adjust, we cannot expect equal opportunity to achieve the highest risk-adjusted returns ever. We tend to be uncertain about outcomes that are too good to be true. We test applications that can be described as

intelligent "factor investing". Preferences for (linear) factors, communication between different factors, non-linear relationships, analysis to rescale these effects in the event of regime change, or industry-specific considerations are important considerations when historical data is used to derive rules. These are some of the factors. Machine learning performance improvements are actually incremental rather than revolutionary.

2. Related Works

Bank deposits, stocks and securities were found to be the major public financial investments (Narayana, 1976). An important structural space for enabling stock trading lies within a country's shareholder population (Gupta, 1987). (Mudra-SAMIR`S, 1992) found that one-fifth of India's national income is set aside as savings. Investors should provide sufficient and reliable information to provide a formative opinion (Jawahar Lal, 1995). The safety aspects of recent issues related to stocks, bonds and shares purchased on stock exchanges are not recognized by most investors. Excessive bridging of different investors and lack of orientation towards asymmetric information are related (Abhijit Dutta, 2000).

John McCarthy coined the term "artificial intelligence" in 1956. The Oxford English Dictionary defines AI as "the theory and advancement of computer systems that can perform tasks requiring human intelligence, such as speech recognition, visual recognition, and decision-making. Translation between languages." [Financial Stability Board, 2017]. AI is defined by [Financial Stability Board, 2017] as "the theory and development of computer systems capable of performing tasks that normally require human intelligence." Both are very broad definitions. AI is described by [Kaplan, 2016] as follows: "The core of AI is actually the core of intelligence, the ability to do the right standardization in the right way based on limited data." When the scope was wider, they drew conclusions quickly with less derived information and expressed intelligent behaviour.

Predicting the nature of the occurrence of future events is an attempt at prediction that allows decision makers to make constructive decisions. Descriptive methods and time series methods are his two main forecasting methods. The causal relationship between inputs and outputs is maintained through explanatory predictions. Assuming consistent cause-and-effect relationships, changing information according to explanatory predictions can predict some consequential effect on the output of the system. By predicting time series, unlike descriptive forecasting, we treat the system as a black box and discover the factors that influence its behaviour. There are two reasons why systems should be created as black boxes [Makridakis, 1997]. First, the system is difficult to understand, and even when it is, it is very difficult to assess the context that is important for monitoring its behaviour. Second, it's important to predict what will happen, not why it will happen. One of the least understood areas is said to be financial time series, which has been under scrutiny for some time for well-known reasons. Therefore, this study explicitly focuses on time series forecasting.

A statistical measure of changes in a portfolio of stocks that represents a portion of the total market is the definition of a stock market index. Indices for a particular market represent market fluctuations. A small market sample that characterizes the entire market is representative of the market index. Market performance is measured by an index, and changes in index prices refer to relative changes in the stocks included in the index. [Fama, 1965] first introduced the term "efficient market," stating that in an efficient market, on average, the overall effect of up-to-date information on intrinsic value is directly reflected in the original price. It is stated again that it will be done. Rapid diffusion of news is believed to occur when

information emerges and is subsequently incorporated into the cost of securities without delay. "Buy-or-hold" strategies aside, these assumptions mean that a technical evaluation of a security or a fundamental evaluation of a company will not yield any more impressive returns to investors.

[Cabalcante et al. [2016] recently conducted a study on computational intelligence applications in financial markets and published it in 2016. This includes studies conducted between 2009 and 2015. In addition to exploring this area and describing the research conducted, they also propose methodologies for building intelligent trading systems. This is different from an overview, as this systematic mapping is very focused, so it is not just a prediction, but multiple types of problems that are being attempted to be solved in terms of AI approaches in financial markets. It contains. These summarize the included studies according to what the main research goal was and what techniques were used. Additionally, questions have been raised about what input variables and techniques were used and whether it is a trading system. The results obtained in preparing this work in terms of questions can be classified as questions that start with the same content as this article, but are broader in terms of topics and techniques.

Bahrammirzaee conducted a study in 2010 on his three types of AI technologies used in three categories of financial applications [Bahrammirzaee, 2010]. The three types of economic problems are credit evaluation, portfolio management, and financial forecasting and planning. There are three types of AI techniques being considered for these financial problems: ANN, expert systems, and hybrid intelligent systems. Soni conducted a study [Soni, 2011] with the descriptive title "Application of ANN in Stock Market Forecasting: A Survey" published in 2011 to discuss the application of ANN in stock market. A year earlier, in his 2010, Li and Ma also conducted a study with the descriptive title "Application of Artificial Neural Networks in Financial Economics: A Survey" [Li and Ma, 2010]. There were reviews on his two types of markets: stock market and foreign exchange. Additionally, applications for bankruptcy and financial crisis prediction were reviewed. The studied application of ANN to exchange rate prediction is proposed in [Yu et al., 2007]. In addition to considering this issue, the question of whether exchange rates are predictable was also considered when considering this issue from an ANN perspective.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Motivation for the Study

Financial markets play a central role in the economic development of various countries. By comparison, behavioral finance can also be an innovative field. However, using behavioral psychology to inform financial decision-making is an evolving field of research. With this in mind, it's easy to understand why rationalists often make illogical decisions about money and investments. The ability to predict trends in financial markets is not only positive through economic gains and mitigation of economic losses, but also helps predict future trends in countries and regions.

Behavioral finance can be an ally in research that investigates the influence of psychology on market outcomes to understand different outcomes in different sectors and industries. Assessing the influence of psychological biases is one of the main components of behavioral finance research. Therefore, the researcher chose this study to evaluate the behaviour of investors.

The types of research being conducted, the topics covered, and how they might provide future researchers and students with information on where gaps can be filled or entry points into future research in AI and finance. Knowledge about how much to give an idea about. You can find market forecasts. Much more research work is being done on this topic, but the challenge is finding new perspectives.

If it's difficult to get an overview, it can become a time-consuming problem. The broad overview will also be of interest to people outside the computer science field. For people in this category, it may not be necessary to delve into all soft computing techniques, and a broad overview may be sufficient. Systematic mapping is used in various research fields and increasingly in software development. Although prediction is widespread as AI is used in the market, validation is less common and there is no systematic map of this scope and goal.

3.2. Purpose of the Study: Motivation

The objective of the present study is to know the investment behaviour of the investors of Guntur District towards the Stock Market.

3.3. Efficient Market Theory (EMT)

The EMT statement [Cuthbertson, 1996] concerns: (1) the recognition that true stock prices affect stock prices. (2) The dominance of logical, profit-increasing actors and the lack of arbitrage opportunities in the economy; (3) the assumption that existing information randomly enters the market and affects market prices. A common methodological notation is used by investors to create expectations for stock prices.

$$E(p_{j,t+1} | \phi_t) = [1 + E(r_{j,t+1} | \phi_t)] p_{jt} \quad (1)$$

From equation (1), if the expected value operator is E, the price of security j at time t+1 is $p_{j,t+1}$, and $r_{j,t+1}$ during period t+1 is the return and quantity of the security. is. The information available to investors at time t is ϕ_t . The expected final price of stock j is given by the left-hand side of the equation $E(p_{j,t+1} | \phi_t)$ provided at the beginning of period ϕ_t . Like stock j, the expected future return of a stock consisting of equal risks is denoted on the right by $1 + E(r_{j,t+1} | \phi_t)$.

According to the available information, under the efficient market hypothesis, market participants can only earn more by chance. The degree of overvaluation or undervaluation of each stock is given as [28]:

$$x_{j,t+1} = p_{j,t+1} - E(p_{j,t+1} | \phi_t) \quad (2)$$

From equation (2), the extent to which the real price of security j deviates from the investor's expected price based on the available information ϕ_t near the end of the period is given as $x_{j,t+1}$. Formula (3)

$$E(x_{j,t+1} | \phi_t) = 0 \quad (3)$$

This shows that all information is included in the stock price. Therefore, according to the EMH, a logical prediction of the return of a particular stock can be referred to as: EQU (4):

$$P_{t+1} = E_t P_{t+1} + \epsilon_{t+1} \quad (4)$$

Here the stock price is P_t . The expected error is ϵ_{t+1} . Therefore, $P_{t+1} - E_t P_{t+1}$ should be zero on average and is independent of the information ϕ_t . Furthermore, if we assume that the random variable (good news or bad news) and the expected value of the prediction error are 0, then $E(x_{j,t+1} | \phi_t) = 0$, which is (5).

$$E_t \epsilon_{t+1} = E_t (P_{t+1} - E_t P_{t+1}) \rightarrow E_t P_{t+1} - E_t P_{t+1} \equiv 0 \quad (5)$$

It is pertinent to note that under the primary market hypothesis, the expectation of stock returns and the arbitrariness of security returns are perfectly consistent.

3.4. Population and Sampling

A set of exclusive characteristics is formed to make the population a holistic group of individuals. The research population must be a subset of the target population available for research. Therefore, limiting the research to at least one or more samples is done on the basis of the population. This is because the population usually consists of a large number of people who can be conveniently screened. Because most of the knowledge about two particular population parameters is contained in carefully selected samples, the population can make practical inferences and derive multiple populations from that sample. To analyse the current study, a sophisticated questionnaire was developed using simple random sampling method and distributed to 200 investors (including men and women) in Guntur, Andhrapradesh.

3.5. Data Collection

Data collection is a technique for gathering and determining information about variables of interest, testing hypotheses, and evaluating results. Commonly used methods are published in literature sources, surveys, interviews, documents and records. Primary data was collected from the selected sample participants and secondary data was obtained from magazines and the internet.

4. Market Interactions of Artificial Intelligence Systems

What is often ignored when talking about AI systems is that these systems need to interact with humans, which can be a difficult partnership, but they usually interact with each other. Interaction between autonomous machines is currently one of the latest research areas for AI and multi-agent systems. The more complex autonomous AI systems are, the more likely they are to interact and learn with unintended consequences. A critical case in financial markets where this kind of interaction definitely occurs is pricing and trading. Applications of algorithmic decision-making emerged early in organized markets. The AI trading algorithm is specifically designed to help traders price their desired trading volume in a given environment, and the market responds with a market-clearing exchange. Under normal competitive conditions, sellers should try to attract buyers with competitively lower prices.

However, the seller may wish to avoid this competition that reduces profits and instead conclude the contract without lowering the price. Collusion among human traders has been documented primarily in financial markets (and other markets), but it is not easy to orchestrate. All sellers have unilateral incentives to break contracts and secretly discard other people's offers. This inherent instability in cartels makes them vulnerable and typically requires cooperating firms to explicitly exchange (coveted) proposals and promises in order to enter into and maintain agreements. These direct collusive relationships are typically collected by authorities as evidence against cooperating companies in antitrust proceedings.

In recent work [Calvano et al. 2020a, 2020b, 2021a] investigated the market interaction consequences of an AI pricing algorithm that independently learns the pricing strategy to use. Interestingly, these authors demonstrated the persistent ability of reinforcement learning algorithms to not forget to charge high prices. We also showed that sophisticated pricing strategies support these high prices. The strategies that algorithms learn autonomously include implicit and tacit threats of punishment aimed at undermining the interests of competitors. It's as if the techniques discovered by these algorithms include something like, "If you do the same, I'll happily charge you a higher price, but the moment you undercut me, I'll punish you

by undercutting you." It seems as if it contains an announcement of the type "We will give you." "So be careful and avoid price competition."

What is remarkable is that this robust collusive system is created autonomously by algorithms and without explicit communication, so market authorities' can it's about having no evidence. The fact that algorithms autonomously and implicitly reach collusive agreements means that, at least in the current legal environment, companies using these algorithms (and their programmers) cannot be held responsible for the consequences of collusion. It could mean that you can't.

4.2. Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Figure 1: Taxonomy of Artificial Intelligence

Learning from data is a goal of both statistics and ML techniques [Frame et al., 2018]. However, instead of asymptotic statistical processes, ML techniques that are not guided by economic theory have more to do with algorithms. ML techniques focus on obtaining the best predictions, while traditional statistics focuses on hypothesis testing and inference. ML architectures involve minimal centralization rather than more powerful similarity estimation. In the financial literature, ML and DL are relatively closely related to applications. With increased computing power, big data, better algorithms, and fintech developments after the 2008 financial crisis, a pool of ML and DL technologies and applications has emerged.

Figure 1 shows that the situation described in ML mode has never been seen before. The model is designed to generate dynamic out-of-sample predictions using instrumental variables, and the dynamic predictor variables are identified by the model based on a subsample

of the data. The test is then run thousands of times on different subsamples of data. The model does this to learn from the data, improving predictive performance (Van Liebergen, 2017). For example, consumer credit models leverage ML techniques and can generate out-of-sample predictions that improve delinquency rates and delinquency classification rates for credit cardholders. They estimate the cost savings to be between 6 and 25 percent of total damages.

5. Empirical Results

For binary classification, the input of the deep neural network should be characteristics of the AI and historical data. For example, let's say the system sorts sample data to select the best-performing stocks over subsequent weeks. AI uses historical data as input. Binary data is the basic fact of all historical data. That is, whether the stock is bought or not, the next week's performance is discussed. Data reduction occurs weekly, so a sample is generated from the inventory each year.

The model is trained using the training data set. Heterogeneous epochs consist of training, which is an iterative process. As is well known, one use of all training data for backpropagation is an epoch. The number of epochs in this study is prefixed with 50 because 50 epochs are required for the training process to converge. After each epoch, the training process produces a classifier as output, and after 50 epochs it produces 50 different classifiers. The final classifier performance should theoretically be the best. However, the training process did not significantly change the performance of the classifier. This provides deep learning algorithms with sufficient training data. The classifier parameters were optimal because the training process converged after different epochs.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Sample Respondents

Parameters	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	140	70
Female	60	30
Total	200	100
Age		
25-40	68	34
41-60	73	36.5
60 and above	59	29.5
Total	200	100
Status		
Businessmen	91	45.5
Employees	68	34
Others	41	20.5
Total	200	100

Married	161	80.5
Un-Married	39	19.5
Total	200	100

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the sample investors. From the table above, 140 (70%) are male investors and 60 (30%) are female investors. 34% of respondents fall under the age group of 25-40 years, 36.5 fall under the age group of 41-60 years, and the remaining investors (29.5%) are above 60 years of age . Of the 200 samples, 45.5% are entrepreneurs, 34% are employees, and the remaining investors belong to other categories. 161 of the respondents in the sample are married (80.5) and the remaining investors are unmarried (19.5).

Table 2: Respondents Opinion in Trusting while Investing

Response	Frequency	%	Cumulative %
Self	27	13.5	13.5
Friend(s)	44	22	35.5
Broker(s)	56	28	63.5
Expert(s)	73	36.5	100
Total	200	100	100

Figure 2: Graphical View of Opinion in Trusting while Investing

Figure 2 represent the opinions of the sample respondents regarding their confidence in investing in the stock market. The table above assumes that 13.5% of the sample is confident in investing and 22% of the sample is confident in investing. According to this model, they believe the words of their friends before investing, 28% of the sample trusts their broker in their investment activities, and the remaining respondents, i.e. 36.5%, base their investment activities on the words of experts. It is said that they are doing so. Based on the above

information, it is clear that the majority of investors believe in the investment conditions provided by stock brokers and professionals.

Table 3: Opinion of investors regarding share value for investment

Response	Frequency	%	Cumulative %
High Cap	83	41.5	41.5
Mid Cap	49	24.5	66
Small Cap	68	34	100
Total	200	100	100

Figure 3: Graphical View of Opinion of Investors with share value

Table 3 and Figure 3 above show the selection of price ranges for stocks to invest in by our sample investors. 41.5% of the sample respondents prefer investing in large cap stocks, his 24.5% of the sample prefers investing in mid cap stocks and the remaining sample investors are willing to invest in small cap stocks. From the above information, it is clear that most of the respondents in the sample are very interested in investing in large cap stocks. Table 4 and Figure 4 provide examples of investors' opinions regarding their trust in media coverage before investing in the stock market.

Table 4: Respondents Opinion towards Trusting Media Reports While Investing

Response	Frequency	%	Cumulative %
Always	71	35.5	35.5
Frequently	66	33	68.5
Rarely	36	18	86.5
Never	27	13.5	100
Total	200	100	100

Figure 4: Trusting Media Reports

Table 4 and Figure 4 show examples of how investors react when they trust media reports before investing in stocks. Out of a sample of 200, 71 respondents said they trust media reports when investing in stocks, 66 said they often trust media reports when investing, 36 were investors who rarely trusted them, and the remaining 27 said they trusted media reports when investing in stocks, and the rest of the respondents said they do not trust media reports at all when investing in stocks. From the above data, the majority of the sample investors i.e. 68.5% trust media reports when investing.

Table 5: Opinion of the Sample Respondents regarding consideration of Past Performance of a Stock before investing in it

Response	Frequency	%	Cumulative %
Always	123	61.5	61.5
Sometimes	31	15.5	77
Rarely	29	14.5	91.5
Never	17	8.5	100
Total	200	100	100

Figure 5: Existing Stock Market Value

Table 5 and Figure 5 show respondents' views on considering the past performance of stocks before investing. 61.5% of respondents said they always consider a stock's past performance before investing, 15.5% only sometimes, 14.5% of respondents said they rarely consider this, and the rest are minority of respondents i.e., 8.5%, said they never consider a stock's past performance when investing. This suggests that the majority of sample respondents i.e., 61.5% considering the stock's past performance before investing.

Table 6: Respondents opinion towards their capability in assessing the average share value

Response	Frequency	%	Cumulative %
Always	47	23.5	23.5
Sometimes	71	35.5	59
Rarely	44	22	81
Never	38	19	100
Total	200	100	100

Figure 6: Assessment of the average share value

Table 6 and Figure 6 show respondents' opinions regarding their ability to estimate the average price of a stock. Out of a sample of 200, 47 investors said they could judge stock prices, 71 said they sometimes could, and 44 said they rarely could. The remaining 38 respondents said they had never evaluated stock prices because they lacked the knowledge, skills and information to avoid incorrect predictions, putting their self-predictions at risk. From the above

information, it is clear that only a small number of sample respondents i.e., 38 investors opined that they never judge the stock price.

Table 7: Investors’ Perception on Experiencing Losses Subsequently

Perception	Frequency	%	Cumulative %
Losses are common in investments	69	34.5	34.5
Had I been more careful, I could have avoided losses	52	26	60.5
I don't want this to be repeated in future	43	21.5	82
A Few decisions are to be avoided when we are not fully confident	36	18	100
Total	200	100	100

Figure 7: Sample investors after experiencing losses

Table 7 and Figure 7 provide an interpretation of the wisdom of the sample investors who suffered investment losses. 34.5% of respondents claim that losses should be shared when investing, 26% claim that people should be more careful to avoid losses, and 21.5% of respondents believe that investment failures will be repeated in the future and the remaining 18% believe they should avoid making investment mistakes. It is noteworthy that most of the investors (i.e., 34.5% respondents) believed that losses are common in investing. Table 8 and Figure 8 below show the emotions and psychological state of investors after purchasing profitable stocks without believing in them.

5.1. Research Hypotheses (RH)

RH₀ = Investors are contented after purchasing lucrative stock with suspicion

RH₁ = Investors are not contented after purchasing lucrative stock with suspicion

Table 8: Investors Perception after Purchasing a Lucrative Stock with Suspicion

Perception	Frequency	%	Cumulative %
Felt happy for deciding odds	93	46.5	46.5
It is sheer luck	41	20.5	67
Go cautiously and sell when you get expected returns	34	17	84
Have maximum returns from it and hold it for long	32	16	100
Total	200	100	100

Figure 8: Articulates the feelings of the investors

Table 9: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	<i>df</i>	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.918 ^a	6	.031
Likelihood Ratio	13,986	6	.030
No of Valid Cases	200		

^a0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.69 (Table 9).

Figure 9: Graphical view of Chi-Square Test

Table 10: Symmetric Measures

Nominal by Nominal		Value	Approximate Significance
	Phi Cramer's V	.162	.031
		.114	.031
	No of Valid Cases	200	

Figure 10: Visual representation of Symmetric Measures

Table 8 above shows investors' disbelief after purchasing a profitable stock. Out of 200 respondents, 93 said they bought money-making stocks with scepticism but were very satisfied, 41 said they were lucky or a gift from heaven, and 34 said they tread carefully and buy as much as possible. They answered that they thought it would be better to sell their stocks as soon as possible and the rest of the investors (i.e. 32 people) felt that it was better to hold the stock for a long time to get the maximum profit. From the data collected above, it is clear that most investors (93 respondents) are cautious about purchasing profitable stocks (Table 9 and Figure

9). The applied Cramer V test tests this correlation since both variables are categorical. The test statistic (0.114) suggests a moderate positive effect of buying profitable stocks with mistrust. The test is significant because the approximate significance value (.031) is less than 0.05. In other words, buying profitable stocks with suspicion can have a positive effect. Therefore, the null hypothesis can be accepted (Table 10 and Figure 10).

5.2. Dependant Variable

Group 1: Investors have experience of <5 years

Group 2: Investors have an experience of >5 years

Independent Variables: Herd Behaviour, Regret Aversion Bias, Loss Repugnance Bias, Regret Aversion Bias, Representativeness bias, Perceptive Dissonance Bias, Brashness bias, and Anchoring Bias.

Table 11: Losses agonised by well-informed and ignorant investors

		Loss on Portfolio					
Ignorant Investors		No Loss	<10%	10-30%	31-50%	Above 50%	Total
	Count	26	33	12	9	3	83
	% within Invt. Expc.	31.3	39.7	14.4	11	3.6	100
	% of Total	13	16.5	6	4.5	1.5	41.5
Well-Informed Investors	Count	31	52	13	15	6	117
	% within Invt. Expc.	26.5	44.44	11.11	12.8	5.15	100
	% of Total	15.5	26	6.5	7.5	3	58.5
Total	Count	57	85	25	24	9	200
	% within Invt. Expc.	28.5	42.5	12.5	12	4.5	100

Figure 11: View of Losses Incurred

The data illustrates the losses encountered by both less experienced and experienced investors in their investments. Among less experienced investors, 31.3% never experienced any loss,

while 39.7% faced losses below 10%. Additionally, 14.4% suffered losses between 10-30%, 11% faced losses between 31-50%, and the remaining 3.6% suffered losses exceeding 50%. In contrast, among experienced investors, 26.5% never encountered any loss. A larger proportion, 44.44%, faced losses below 10%. Furthermore, 11.11% experienced losses between 10-30%, 12.8% faced losses between 31-50%, and 5.15% encountered losses surpassing 50%. The data indicates that a higher percentage of experienced investors experienced minimal losses or none at all compared to less experienced investors. However, among those who did face losses, a significant portion in both groups encountered losses below 10%.

5.3. Research Hypotheses

RH₀ = Experience of the investors doesn't have any relation with regard to losses

RH₁ = Experience of the investors have relation with regard to losses

Table 12: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.604	4	.463
Likelihood Ratio	3.649	4	.449
Linear-by-linear Association	1.481	1	.226
N of Valid Cases	200		

*<5 is the anticipated count of 0 cells (0.0%). 8.75 is the minimum anticipated count.

463, .449 and .226 are the p-value from Pearson Chi-Square test, Likelihood Ratio & Linear-by-Linear Association. Table 12 and Figure 12 show that the above analysis shows that the 95% confidence level is adopted as the null hypothesis.

Figure 12: Analysis of Chi-Square

Table 13: Group Statistics (Knowledgeable & Less Knowledgeable)

Experience		Mean	SD	Valid N (List wise)	
				Un-weighted	Weighted
Ignorant Investors	Loss Repugnance	3.083	.5761	83	83
	Regret Aversion	3.021	.7884	83	83
	Herd Behaviour	3.074	.8423	83	83
	Representativeness	2.296	.8461	83	83
	Brashness	2.839	.7602	83	83
	Anchoring	2.596	.5843	83	83
	Perceptive Dissonance	3.263	.7579	83	83
Well-Informed Investors	Loss Repugnance	3.582	.6024	117	117
	Regret Aversion	3.454	.7671	117	117
	Herd Behaviour	3.182	.8653	117	117
	Representativeness	3.308	.7741	117	117
	Brashness	3.559	.7112	117	117
	Anchoring	3.541	.6798	117	117
	Perceptive Dissonance	3.501	.7314	117	117
Total	Loss Repugnance	3.351	.6401	200	200
	Regret Aversion	3.261	.8054	200	200
	Herd Behaviour	3.131	.8557	200	200
	Representativeness	3.306	.8071	200	200

Figure 13: Knowledgeable and Less Knowledgeable

As shown in Table 13 and Figure 13, the exclusion of herd behaviour and boldness bias differs from the average difference between the behavioral tendencies of the investor type groups. However, the selected investor type identifiers that are acceptable or appropriate are represented by another five variables. The status of the individual variables, which mainly support the discriminant function, is checked by group equality test, as shown in Table 14. The null hypothesis is tested using Wilks' lambda test statistic, so the means for both investor groups are equal. Despite the bias-independent variables except collective action and boldness bias, Table 14 confirms the results reported in the group statistics, assuming a high F-test level. This suggests that these three trends are likely to be similarly disclosed by both investor groups.

Table 14: Tests of Equality of Group Means

	Wilks' Lambda	F	df1	df2	Sig.
Loss Repugnance	.847	67.414	1	198	.000
Regret Aversion	.931	28.972	1	198	.000
Herd Behaviour	.993	1.396	1	198	.235
Representativeness	.998	.008	1	198	.921
Brashness	.999	89.883	1	198	.000
Anchoring	.643	207.189	1	198	.000
Perceptive Dissonance	.978	9.841	1	198	.003

Figure 14: Tests of Equality

Table 14 and Figure 14 show that the significance values of perceptual dissonance bias, herd-leading bias, regret aversion bias, loss aversion bias, representativeness bias, herd-leading bias, boldness bias, and anchoring bias are 0.05. Both investor groups appear to disclose the above biases differently, with one investor group being more burdened than the other. The above test is used to check the significant contribution of the independent bias variables to the discriminant function. This is somewhere between 0 and 1 (0 = group means are different, 1 = group means are indistinguishable or identical). It states that the smaller the value of Wilks' lambda, the more important the individual variable is to the discriminant function. The Wilks' lambda values for herding behaviour and boldness are 0.993 and 0.999, confirming the results obtained by group statistics and F-tests in the test of equality of group means. The investment objectives of the sample respondents are shown in Table 15 and Figure 15 below.

Table 15: Objectives of Investment and its Ranking by Respondents

Objectives	Ranking										Total	
	1	%	2	%	3	%	4	%	5	%		
Solid Return	73	36.5	51	25.5	38	19	25	12.5	13	6.5	200	100
Low Risk	64	32	59	29.5	44	22	17	8.5	16	8	200	100
Tax Benefits	58	29	53	26.5	47	23.5	32	16	10	5	200	100
Speculation	53	26.5	50	25	45	22.5	29	14.5	23	11.5	200	100
Capital Gain	49	24.5	46	23	41	20.5	33	16.5	31	15.5	200	100

Figure 15: Ranking of Investments

5.4. Research Outcomes

- A. Many of the sample investors conduct their investment activities by trusting the words of stock brokers and experts.
- B. It is noteworthy that the majority of respondents (i.e. 41.5%) are very interested in investing in large-cap stocks.
- c. The majority of investors (68.5%) trust media reports when investing.
- d. Most of the respondents in the sample i.e., 61.5%, consider the past performance of a stock before investing.
- e. Only a small number of sample respondents (i.e. her 38 investors) felt that they would not judge stock prices due to lack of knowledge, skills, etc.
- f. More than two-thirds of the investors in the sample (i.e., 69 respondents) believe that losses are common in investing.

6. Recommendations for the Investors

The results clearly indicates that this study is conducted to collect information on various behavioral biases that investors engage in. But they don't know much about behavioral finance. Additionally, the study found that many investors fell victim to the various preferences considered in the study. Investors are encouraged to continually strive to improve their knowledge of behavioral finance and hone their skills on the subject. Investors' level of understanding can be improved by learning about various behavioral biases. Therefore, it was discussed to what extent it is likely to be emotionally influenced when deciding on investment plans in ambiguous situations. We strongly recommend that you keep track of the biases in cases to which you are susceptible. In rare cases, higher value investment decisions within the exchange are supported by these records, so these records must be evaluated to retrieve and restore memories. Understanding behavioral biases further enhances rationality improvements, and the appropriateness of biases in investment decisions ultimately increases market efficiency.

The performance of the enhanced prediction systems is assessed with the help of Average Correction Rate (ACR). True Positive Rate (TPR), True Negative Rate (TNR),

Precision and Average Correction Rate (ACR). In (6), EQU (7), EQU (8) and EQU (9), the assessment criteria is denoted:

$$TPR = Recall = \frac{TP}{P} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (6)$$

$$TNR = \frac{TN}{N} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \quad (7)$$

$$AUC = \frac{TPR+TNR}{2} \quad (8)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (9)$$

All positive samples are indicated by P and N. All negative samples will be marked. The number of true positive models is represented by TP, the number of false positive samples is represented by FP, the number of true negative samples is represented by TN, and the number of false negative samples is represented by FN. Furthermore, this study evaluates the performance of the proposed method using stock trading simulation. The evaluation uses four criteria, as well as the stock's maximum average price increase and the stock's maximum average price decline.

Table 16 show the volatility, annual return, average sales, and risk-to-risk ratio for each strategy. If all long and short positions in the portfolio are liquidated, new stocks are introduced, and new stocks are replaced, the new stocks will endure twice the volume (for the short and long baskets respectively). (Specify the weights to total 100%). AI's annual overhead is 4.8x 0.20%, or 0.96% assuming a 20 basis point round trip trade, which corresponds to a position exchange. As already mentioned, only stocks that have more space in the S&P 500 universe and are significantly more liquid are considered. The results can be smaller than overweight and underweight positions associated with benchmarks that do not require true short selling. Up to the downsize bias, the size of returns, risks, and sales are minimized to ensure a consistent return-to-risk ratio.

Table 16: Statistical Analysis of AI strategy

Model	Financial Return	Risk	Ratio	Business Turnover
OLS	0.0%	6.9%	-0.019	3.3
AI	4.1%	11.45%	0.49	5.13

Figure 16: Base case models’ performance in the testing samples

Based on Table 17, we would like to highlight some of our observations. First, we need to consider a linear strategy in the upper range. In theory, OLS found a unique solution that would eventually result in poor performance from the sample, even if it could choose the same weights. Nonlinear nuances in factors are under fitted, while features that are well achieved in the training data may be over fitted.

Table 17: Training Data Set

Test Period 1 Month				
Model	Financial Return	Risk	Ratio	Business Turnover
OLS	0.0%	6.9%	-0.019	3.3
AI	4.1%	11.45%	0.49	5.13
Test Period 1 Year				
Model	Financial Return	Risk	Ratio	Business Turnover
OLS	-2.3	7.1%	-0.36	0.67
AI	2.1%	4.91%	0.391	0.91

Figure 17: Model performance in the testing sample

7. Conclusion

This study investigates investor rationality. Behavioral finance is the fusion of psychology and finance. Behavioral finance offers many new possibilities from a research point of view, but it is above all a challenge because this approach is a rather tenuous idea. Behavioral thinking provides many opportunities for new thinking and research studies because of its emphasis on the human mind and its thinking techniques. Many financial market predictions have been attempted by the general research field of artificial intelligence. The concept of ML lies somewhere between linear regression, evident in typical statistics, and human judgment based on shared experience and discussion.

Contrary to mere enthusiasm, it is accepted that non-ML weapons are not practical weapons for stock selection, so keeping the model relatively simple allows for innovative and better ways to model it. Further efforts are being made to understand. Utilizes AI technology to predict the future stock price index of the stock market. Behavioral economics and behavioral finance are beautifully integrated and provide insight into how we make financial decisions. Multiple behavioral biases to which people are susceptible are frequently investigated. Investors can take comfort in the good news that computer technology can be used to make accurate market predictions.

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